

Human-robot collaboration at work: A review of workers' experiences and interpretations across organisational, team and individual levels

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ABSTRACT

Robotic systems are being introduced into an increasing number of workplaces, where they may influence how work is performed and experienced. Despite their growing presence, the psychological, social and ethical dimensions of human-robot collaboration remain under-explored. This review addresses this gap. It synthesises empirical studies on how workers across diverse domains experience and interpret collaboration with robots and identifies conditions that explain why experiences of human-robot collaboration differ.

Based on 44 peer-reviewed empirical studies published between 2014 and 2024, this review identified three interconnected levels through which these experiences and perceptions unfold: organisational, team and individual. At the organisational level, workers' experiences are shaped by implementation strategies, communication practices and inclusion in decision-making processes. At the team level, robot integration is associated with changes in collaboration patterns and social interactions. At the individual level, workers navigate shifting responsibilities, emotional responses, ethical concerns and professional values.

The findings demonstrate that the impact of human-robot collaboration varies across professions, ranging from minimal disruptions to significant task and workflow transformations. Across studies, variation in experiences and interpretations of human-robot collaboration aligned with two dimensions: the degree of control workers had over robot use and the extent to which robots reshaped core tasks, highlighting implementation strategies and opportunities for participation as key conditions shaping workers' experiences of human-robot collaboration at work.

1. Introduction

Although the digitalisation of work is not a new development, the presence of robots in workplace settings is increasingly portrayed as introducing new forms of interaction and collaboration between humans and robots (Dörrenbächer et al., 2022; Eurofound, 2024). Human-robot collaboration is frequently framed as a site where the capacities of humans and robots intersect (Dörrenbächer et al., 2022). Humans are often described as demonstrating strengths in cognitive flexibility, problem-solving, and adaptability to unexpected events, whereas robots are positioned as excelling at executing repetitive, physically demanding, or precision-oriented tasks (Panagou et al., 2024; Simone et al., 2022). However, such framings risk obscuring the social and organisational dynamics through which human-robot collaboration is negotiated and enacted in practice (Bijker & Pinch, 1987; Sartori &

Theodorou, 2022).

The synergy between human and robotic capabilities has been characterised as a means to enhance productivity (Schmidtler et al., 2015), reduce worker fatigue (Hentout et al., 2019), and enable outcomes perceived as exceeding what either entity could achieve alone (Romero et al., 2016). For some workers, human-robot collaboration has become associated with changes in work tasks, such as acquiring new technical skills or reallocating dangerous and tedious tasks to robots (Smids et al., 2020). At the same time, collaboration with robots has been linked to role simplification, with workers taking on more monotonous or less skill-intensive tasks (Sorell, 2022). This, in turn, is sometimes experienced as a source of stress, discomfort and anxiety, particularly when workers perceive risks to job security (Abeliansky et al., 2024).

Despite the growing presence of robots in various professional fields,

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the implications of mixed human-robot work environments remain underexplored (Weiss et al., 2021). Much existing research is situated within a technological paradigm, focusing on efficiency and productivity (Sorell, 2022), with limited attention to workers' lived and situated experiences (Baltrusch et al., 2022; Weiss et al., 2021). Recent work has begun to foreground experiential dimensions, drawing attention to the psychological, social and ethical entanglements of human-robot collaboration (Apraiz et al., 2023; Elias et al., 2025; T. Turja, Minkkinen, & Mauno, 2022). This line of research has approached human-robot collaboration and its effects with a focus on the individual work experience, for example, workers' performance (Simone et al., 2022), mental workload (Carissoli et al., 2024), safety and ergonomics (Gualtieri et al., 2021) or its impacts on teamwork (Ma et al., 2022). Other prior work adopted multi-level perspectives on human-robot collaboration, yet remains scoped to specific sectors, such as industrial settings (Simões et al., 2022), selected organisational practices, such as leadership (Tsai et al., 2022) or implementation-oriented frameworks (Berx et al., 2025; Callari et al., 2025). While these studies provide insights into specific contexts and configurations of human-robot collaboration, a broader, overarching mapping that systematically characterises and contrasts these variations is still lacking. This relates to growing calls for deeper insights into how humans and robots could or should work together (Baltrusch et al., 2022) and how workers experience collaborations with non-humans in the context of work (Sadeghian & Hassenzahl, 2022).

Our focus is on human-robot collaboration, here understood as workers interacting with robots across various work contexts. In this review, work refers specifically to employment-based work, defined by the International Labour Organization (ILO) as work performed for pay or profit, thereby excluding unpaid, volunteer or domestic labour (Gammarano, 2019).² According to the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE), robots are physically embodied machines with autonomy that can sense their environment, make decisions, and accomplish tasks (Guizzo, 2024). In workplace settings, robots may take many forms and fulfil a range of functions (Eurofound, 2024). Robot types included in this review are industrial, service, social, exoskeletons, surgical, and therapeutic robots, but purely software-based systems lacking a physical presence were excluded. By focusing on physically embodied robots, the engagement with robots in shared physical space is foregrounded. However, our main interest is not the technical characteristics of different robot types, but the ways in which humans and robots collaborate in workplace settings. Multiple robot types are therefore included because the unit of analysis is workers' experiences and interpretations of human-robot collaboration at work. In this review, robots are treated as cases through which we explore how work is influenced, reconfigured, and interpreted across different contexts.

Taking an exploratory approach, we examine how human-robot collaboration is experienced and interpreted by workers in situated, context-dependent ways. We integrate empirical research across organisational, team, and individual levels and interpret our findings through a sociotechnical lens (Bijker & Pinch, 1987; Latour, 1999; Orlikowski, 2000). A sociotechnical perspective conceptualises technological change as co-produced by the reciprocal alignment of social and technical elements. It further acknowledges that the practical use of technology is determined by how workers construct and adapt its purpose to meet the specific demands of their work environment (Bijker & Pinch, 1987; Orlikowski, 2000). From this perspective, technology use is given meaning by its actual integration into everyday work practices which can differ from the intended use defined by designers, developers

or management (Orlikowski, 2000). Constructivist accounts emphasise that the same technology may be interpreted and enacted differently by different groups of users (Bijker & Pinch, 1987). Importantly, these processes are shaped not only by the technology and its immediate users, but also by the surrounding context (Latour, 1999). In organisational settings, this can include workplace materials, conditions, structures, and other arrangements for integrating technology into work practices.

This review contributes to the existing literature by expanding the focus beyond a single sector to encompass a broader range of cases involving workers from multiple sectors and various types of robots. The analysis examines workers' experiences on three levels (individual, team, and organisational) and demonstrates that relational, social, and ethical aspects play a crucial role in how human-robot collaboration is perceived and enacted. In doing so, this review addresses a gap in prior research, which often overlooks how human-robot collaboration is negotiated and given meaning by those working closely with robots (Baltrusch et al., 2022; Weiss et al., 2021).

While we apply established definitions of work and robots (e.g. paid employment and physically embodied, autonomous robots), we also acknowledge that such definitions reflect specific institutional and disciplinary framings (e.g., ILO, IEEE), which shape what is rendered visible in research on human-robot collaboration, i.e., what counts as work and what qualifies as a robot. This leads to the following research questions guiding this literature review: (1) How do workers experience and interpret human-robot collaboration? (2) What differences exist in workers' experiences across different domains?

In this context, 'experiences' refer to workers' lived, embodied interactions with robots, encompassing their emotional responses, practical challenges and everyday encounters. Meanwhile, 'interpretations' refer to how workers make sense of these encounters. This includes how they view their own roles and those of robots, how they assign meaning to the collaboration, and how they articulate expectations or values concerning the technology. The remainder of the article will first outline the methodology, then present the characteristics of the selected studies, followed by the thematic findings. These findings will then be discussed in light of broader implications for robot implementation at workplaces.

2. Methods

2.1. Search strategy and selection process

The literature search was conducted in two stages across three databases Scopus, Web of Science and SocIndex. Scopus and Web of Science were selected for their broad coverage of peer-reviewed journals and conferences across disciplines. SocIndex was included to incorporate a social science perspective. This combination was intended to ensure coverage of diverse disciplines, e.g., engineering, human-computer interaction, and the social sciences, reflecting the interdisciplinary nature of the research questions.

To align the search outcomes with the focus of the review, how workers in various industry domains experience and interpret working with robots, a three-part search string was developed. The search string targeted (1) human-robot collaboration, (2) professional work contexts and (3) experiential dimensions of work.

The first component included the terms *cobot**, "human-robot system*", and *robotisation* to capture diverse collaborative configurations. These terms were chosen to reflect the language used in both engineering and interdisciplinary literature. The second component focused on capturing professional or industrial contexts, using terms like "workplace," "profession*," and "work environment*" to ensure relevance to working professionals rather than general users or other application contexts. The third component referred to work experiences and perceptions, incorporating the terms "job satisfaction," "task significance," "repetitive task*" and "dissatisfaction". Broader terms, such as "perception", "purpose" and "skill", were included to allow for the identification of diverse conceptualisations of work experience based on

² To promote clarity and consistency, the term "workers" will be predominantly used throughout this review when referring to individuals in various work roles. We acknowledge that terms such as "professionals" and "employees" are also fitting; however, the results section will employ more specific terms (e.g., care workers, physiotherapists) when discussing particular occupational groups.

related literature. Keyword selection was informed by the terminology used in related literature on automation and work settings (e.g. Smids et al., 2019; Baltrusch et al., 2022). An overview of the applied keywords is presented in Table 1. Each search string included synonyms or related concepts while accounting for different spelling conventions.

The search yielded 867 results. After removing 240 duplicates, the first author screened 627 abstracts. A selection of 151 articles was divided among the three other authors to sharpen the eligibility criteria in a collaborative effort. The final overview of eligibility criteria is presented in Table 2. For this review, studies were included only if they involved participants with direct, embodied experience of working with robots. Studies that asked participants to speculate, imagine or evaluate hypothetical or video-based interactions were excluded. Studies involving virtual environments were also excluded due to the lack of shared physical presence, which was considered central to the understanding of human-robot collaboration in situated work contexts. Additionally, articles were excluded if they: (1) were not related to human-robot interaction or collaborative robots in the work context; (2) were not empirical studies; or (3) were published before 2014. Following the screening process, 54 articles were retrieved in full and assessed against the eligibility criteria, resulting in a total of 13 articles.

Given the number of eligible studies, a second search was conducted to identify additional relevant publications using an expanded, yet aligned, search strategy. This search was performed in Scopus using the broad search terms 'robot* AND work* AND experience' to capture additional studies using alternative terminology. The same inclusion and exclusion criteria from the first search phase were applied. Non-relevant technological aspects (e.g., AI, chatbots, virtual reality) and non-relevant formats (e.g., reviews, pilot studies) were excluded. While we excluded these articles to maintain the focus of the review, we acknowledge that, in particular, pilot studies and studies with other populations, such as students, may offer valuable insights into aspects of mental health, workload, acceptance, and the perceived potential and limitations of robots in workplace settings. They may provide early indications of how novel robot designs or work practices might influence collaboration, highlight ethical or psychological considerations, and inform hypotheses for later, real-world testing. These nuances and indications could inform future research directions and deepen the understanding of how experiences and interpretations of working with robots are shaped. However, these types of studies differ from real-world worker experiences, as participants are asked to consider hypothetical scenarios and imagine their reactions, emotions and interpretations.

The second search yielded 1516 articles. Following title and abstract screening, 117 full-text articles were assessed for eligibility by the first author. This process resulted in 31 additional articles that met the inclusion criteria. In total, 44 empirical articles were included in this

Table 1
Keywords used in the search string for the first search.

Keyword category	Keywords used
Keywords related to collaborative robots	cobot* OR co-bot* OR "collaborative robot*" OR "human-robot interaction" OR "human-robot collaboration" OR "human-robot system*" OR "human-robot cooperation" OR "robotization" OR "robotisation"
Keywords related to work context	"work environment*" OR "workplace" OR "work condition*" OR profession* OR "work context"
Keywords related to work experience	"meaningful work" OR "meaningful job" OR "meaningful" OR "meaningfulness" OR "job quality" OR "work quality" OR "work satisfaction" OR "job satisfaction" OR "autonomy" OR "belonging" OR "task significance" OR purpos* OR "job crafting" OR "job design" OR "skill*" OR "work engag*" OR "job engag*" OR "employee engag*" OR "employee satisfaction" OR "worthwhile work" OR "decent work" OR "good work" OR perception OR perceiv* OR experience OR "work experience" OR meaningless* OR replac* OR "repetitive task*" OR dissatisfaction

Table 2
Overview of eligibility criteria.

Category	Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Study Type	Empirical research (e.g., case studies, qualitative studies, quantitative studies)	Reviews, conceptual papers, pilot studies, editorials
Context	Human-robot collaboration in work settings	Non-work-related human-robot interaction
Participants	Workers with direct experience using robots	Students, participants imagining robot use
Technology	Physical robots used in workplaces	AI-only systems, virtual agents, chatbots
Publication Date	2014 – present	Articles published before 2014

literature review. The screening and selection process is summarised in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Flow diagram of the literature search and selection process.

2.2. Data analysis

Key information from the 44 articles was systematically extracted into a data extraction table. It included details such as the research design, participant characteristics, types, and functions of robots, workers' exposure to robots and reported experiences, challenges and possibilities of working with robots. The first author performed the initial data extraction and drafted the data extraction table. The findings from the table were discussed with the other authors, resulting in a summary table (see [Appendix A](#)).

A thematic analysis approach was adopted, informed by the principles of (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Initial coding involved extracting findings from each article and identifying recurring focus points, e.g., perceived improvements, anxiety, social interactions, role redefinitions, lack of involvement, reskilling, risk of deskilling, concerns, ambivalence, fears, and adaptation. Categories were developed through iterative engagement with the articles, guided by patterns identified in the articles and informed by the researchers' interpretive judgement (Graneheim et al., 2017).

Coded segments were compared and grouped into broader thematic constructions with attention to both shared patterns and divergences across contexts. For example, codes related to workers' internal responses (e.g. anxiety, risk for deskilling, role redefinitions) were initially grouped under the category of 'individual experience'. These were later developed into more focused subthemes like 'mental health risks' and 'shifts in work tasks'. This interpretive clustering contributed to the construction of three analytical levels, organisational, team and individual, which served as lenses through which to explore the experiences of human-robot collaboration. These levels are not presented as rigid categories but as analytic configurations that may help make sense of how experiences of working with robots are patterned, negotiated, and situated. The initial coding and theme construction were led by the first author. The co-authors cross-checked and verified the coded data and themes, flagging any uncertainties, inconsistencies, or disagreements. These points were then discussed in team meetings until mutual

agreement was reached.

3. Results

The aim of this literature review is to explore the experiences and interpretations of workers collaborating with robots and examine differences between work domains. The findings are presented in two stages. First, a descriptive mapping outlines key features of the selected studies. Following this, an in-depth analysis explores how workers' experiences and meaning-making processes are represented in the reviewed studies, with attention to recurring tensions, framings and situated understandings of human-robot collaboration.

3.1. Descriptive results

The 44 included studies reflect a heterogeneous and fragmented research landscape, illustrating how human-robot collaboration is addressed across different work domains, robots and methodological approaches. As presented in the summary table ([Appendix A](#)), studies differ in focus, scope and framing, offering a picture of how collaboration between humans and robots is situated in working life.

Healthcare was the most represented domain, accounting for nearly half of the studies ($n = 20$), followed by manufacturing ($n = 8$), hospitality ($n = 4$), agriculture ($n = 3$), logistics ($n = 2$), service ($n = 2$), and education ($n = 1$). An additional four studies compared multiple sectors (Lloyd & Payne, 2023; Nikolova et al., 2024; Turja et al., 2024; Yam et al., 2022). [Fig. 2](#) visualises this distribution. Most studies ($n = 40$) addressed a single domain and within these, 29 considered multiple professional roles, while 15 focused on homogeneous groups of workers. Thirteen studies explicitly examined experiences at different hierarchical levels. For instance, they compared frontline workers' views with those of managers and board members. This highlighted how organisational position may shape both experiences of robots and the framing of their value.

The kind of robots varied widely. Some articles focused on industrial

Fig. 2. Distribution of work domains.

robots deployed in production or logistics ($n = 11$), others on surgical robots in healthcare settings ($n = 5$) and service robots in hospitality ($n = 5$), while others studied robotic animals ($n = 3$) or social robots such as the NAO model ($n = 3$) used in emotionally or cognitively supportive roles. Four studies (Lloyd & Payne, 2023; Turja et al., 2024; Vogt & König, 2023; Yam et al., 2022) included multiple types of robots, often in cross-sectional comparison.

Methodologically, the reviewed literature was dominated by qualitative approaches ($n = 31$), including interviews ($n = 28$), observations ($n = 7$), field visits ($n = 6$) and focus groups ($n = 5$). These studies often aimed to capture situated experiences, workplace dynamics and tacit knowledge. Quantitative methods were used in eight studies. The most deployed quantitative method was surveys ($n = 10$), often used to generalise findings across large or diverse populations. Five studies employed a mixed methods design, combining in-depth qualitative work with structured quantitative data collection.

Studies varied widely in their reporting of the temporal scope. As shown in Table 3, nearly half ($n = 20$) did not specify the study's length, and most involved short-term engagements, often lasting less than two months ($n = 10$). The majority relied on a single data collection period, often focusing on brief interactions between workers and robots. Only three studies involved follow-up visits (Bäcman et al., 2020; Huisman & Kort, 2019; Turjamaa et al., 2023).

Geographically, the studies were conducted across 21 countries, as shown in Fig. 3. Most focused on a single country ($n = 40$), while four offered comparative insights (He et al., 2023; Lloyd & Payne, 2023; Nikolova et al., 2024; Yam et al., 2022). The geographical distribution was concentrated on high-income, industrialised countries, with no studies including perspectives from low-income countries.

3.2. Thematic results

This review analysed 44 peer-reviewed articles to explore how workers, across different workplace settings, experience and interpret collaboration with robots. The synthesis is structured around three interpretive levels: organisational, team and individual. Fig. 4 illustrates these analytical levels and their respective sub-dimensions. Across the reviewed articles, human-robot collaboration was described as shaping and being shaped by dynamics at each of these levels in distinct, yet interrelated ways.

3.2.1. Organisational level: how do organisational logics and practices configure workers' relations with robots?

Many of the reviewed articles suggest that organisational strategies for robot implementation shape how workers relate to robots, influencing their reported acceptance, motivation and willingness to collaborate. Five studies reported that excluding workers from the decision-making process was associated with mistrust, and in some cases, with the avoidance or non-adoption of robots (Berkers et al., 2023; Huisman & Kort, 2019; Schumacher et al., 2022; Welfare et al., 2019; Wurhofer et al., 2015). In a narrative interview study conducted by Wurhofer et al. (2015), set in a semiconductor factory including both

operators and supervisors, the implementation process was described as top-down and workers recounted feelings of 'resignation' (Wurhofer et al., 2015, p. 213), linked to their exclusion from the introduction of robotic systems. Some participants even reported experiencing 'malicious joy' (Wurhofer et al., 2015, p. 213) when robots made mistakes, interpreting these failures as signs that their expertise had been overlooked (Wurhofer et al., 2015).

A comparative study by Berkers et al. (2023) conducted across eight Dutch warehouses with a total of 26 employees in order pick and pack tasks and ten employees with managerial responsibilities, highlighted how participatory strategies such as idea competitions, discussions during appraisal meetings and project workshops were described as aligning implementation more closely with workers' situated expertise. In these contexts, job tasks were reportedly adjusted in ways to reflect workers' preferences. In contrast, when robot deployment prioritised technical performance over workers' input, participants described misalignments in task design and expressed concerns about reduced autonomy and job downgrading (Berkers et al., 2023). Worker involvement in early discussions around task allocation, role development and workflow integration was interpreted as contributing to a shared understanding of the robot's purpose and function (Berkers et al., 2023; Paluch et al., 2022). Conversely, in workplaces where integration strategies were unclear, workers reported experiencing ambiguity, hesitancy, and confusion (Huisman & Kort, 2019), as well as the circulation of rumours about the robots' functionalities and their impact on the work environment (Meissner et al., 2020; Wurhofer et al., 2015). This was seen to diminish motivation and increase feelings of helplessness (Meissner et al., 2020).

Three studies noted how robots were introduced could also shape how workers compared their own abilities with those of robots, occasionally giving rise to competitive dynamics (Chigbu & Nekhwevha, 2022; Mejia et al., 2024; Ngcwangu, 2023). When organisational communication did not clearly address the implications of robot integration for roles or required skills, workers described drawing comparisons between their own abilities and those of robots. These comparisons appeared to elicit a range of responses, from motivation to anxiety, as illustrated by the following examples from the hospitality and manufacturing industries. In one case, restaurant servers reportedly challenged themselves to deliver food faster than the robotic assistants (Mejia et al., 2024), while some factory workers reflected on feelings of inadequacy when robots operated without breaks (Chigbu & Nekhwevha, 2022). These reflections were often linked to concerns about the perceived devaluation of human contributions in increasingly automated environments (Chigbu & Nekhwevha, 2022; Mejia et al., 2024; Ngcwangu, 2023).

Beyond formal implementation strategies, the management's role was frequently described as influential in shaping workers' interpretations of robotic integration, especially in studies conducted in manufacturing and service sectors (Meissner et al., 2020; Paluch et al., 2022). Workers who recalled previous experiences with supportive management during technological transitions were more likely to frame robot adaptation as beneficial (Paluch et al., 2022). In contrast, when prior transitions were experienced as abrupt or imposed, some workers tended to approach robot adoption with scepticism or resistance (Meissner et al., 2020). In the explorative interview study with service sector employees of mixed backgrounds, Paluch et al. (2022) also noted that early and transparent communication about responsibilities and workflows was perceived as helpful in aligning expectations and fostering trust in the robot integration process (Paluch et al., 2022).

The availability and perceived quality of training also emerged as a factor in workers' reflections on adaptation and collaboration (He et al., 2023; Kang et al., 2016; Liu et al., 2024; Moloney et al., 2024; Schuessler et al., 2020; Silveira Thomas Porto & Catal, 2021; Şenol Çelik et al., 2024). He et al. (2023), for instance, found in their quantitative study involving employees in various roles in the hospitality sector that improved robot knowledge was associated with reduced uncertainty and

Table 3
Temporal scope of studies.

Duration	Articles	Comments
Less than one month	5	Ranging from 2 days of data collection to 2 weeks
1-5 months	12	5 cases of 2 months of data collection, 3 cases that took about one month for data collection and 2 cases for 3 months and 4 months respectively
6-12 months	4	Four different periods of time: 6 months, 7,5 months, 9 and 10 months
1-2 years	2	One year and 1,5 years
2+ years	1	Data from 2005 to 2021 for statistical analysis
Not specified	20	

Fig. 3. Geographical distribution of countries where studies were conducted.

Fig. 4. Overview of the three analytical levels, covering organisational, team and individual aspects.

enhanced teamwork efficiency. By contrast, a lack of training was linked to reports of stress, unclear responsibilities and safety concerns in studies in the healthcare sector (Kang et al., 2016; Moloney et al., 2024). In robot-assisted surgery settings, characterised by shifting procedures and team structures, several studies noted that inconsistencies in training appeared to increase stress and disrupt team coordination (Kang

et al., 2016; Moloney et al., 2024; Şenol Çelik et al., 2024). Conversely, access to consistent training was associated with improved collaboration and reduced strain (Schuessler et al., 2020; Silveira Thomas Porto & Catal, 2021).

While formal training was viewed as central to organisational support, two studies also described how peer-led learning and informal

learning practices emerged in the absence of adequate organisational guidance (Lambrechts et al., 2021; Yuan et al., 2022). For example, in a mixed-methods study involving four high-volume distribution centres, Lambrecht et al. (2021) found that peer-led exchanges were associated with increased confidence and reduced hesitation when working with robots. (Lambrechts et al., 2021). In contrast, limited communication or management involvement was associated with confusion and disengagement (Huisman & Kort, 2019).

In some sectors, especially healthcare and manufacturing, experienced workers were reported to assume informal training roles to address gaps in organisational support (Kang et al., 2016; Lloyd & Payne, 2023; Persson et al., 2023; Read et al., 2020). While these unofficial teaching practices were seen to foster team cohesion and support integration of robots, they also added to the workload and, in some cases, led to frustration, especially when not formally recognised or supported by the organisation (Kang et al., 2016).

3.2.2. Team level: how do human–robot relations emerge and evolve in collaborative team contexts?

In the reviewed literature, robots were framed as having the potential to act as isolators (Bäcman et al., 2020; Lim et al., 2024; Meissner et al., 2020; Paluch et al., 2022; Turjamaa et al., 2023; Welfare et al., 2019) and as facilitators of human interaction and collaboration (Barker & Jewitt, 2023; Beran et al., 2020; Hansen, 2015; Lambrechts et al., 2021; Persson et al., 2023; Read et al., 2020; Vogt & König, 2023; Wurhofer et al., 2015).

Besides concerns about job loss or replacement (Chen & Cai, 2024; Ngcwangu, 2023; Stankevičiūtė et al., 2021; Welfare et al., 2019; Yam et al., 2022), another prominent concern of working alongside robots was seen in a potential risk of robots acting as an isolator of social interaction. Several studies across different domains brought up participants' fears of increased social isolation at work (Bäcman et al., 2020; Lim et al., 2024; Meissner et al., 2020; Paluch et al., 2022; Turjamaa et al., 2023; Welfare et al., 2019). Although none of the reviewed articles presented direct evidence of reduced social interaction or increased isolation due to robot implementation, several studies reported that workers were concerned about the potential long-term effects on social connection, particularly in when tasks were shared with robots (Lim et al., 2024; Meissner et al., 2020; Paluch et al., 2022; Welfare et al., 2019). In care settings, such concerns also extended to care receivers (Bäcman et al., 2020; Turjamaa et al., 2023).

These concerns reflect that social interactions were understood by workers as valued components of workplace life (Welfare et al., 2019), contributing to a sense of belonging (Paluch et al., 2022), offering emotional support and facilitating the exchange of both professional and personal knowledge (Meissner et al., 2020). Robots were often not perceived as capable of social behaviour in the same way as human coworkers (Lim et al., 2024; Paluch et al., 2022). In Lim et al.'s (2024) mixed-methods study examining the implementation of robotic nurse assistants, nurses identified companionship as an area for improvement, noting that robotic nurse assistants lacked the ability to engage in interactive conversations (Lim et al., 2024).

In two studies, homecare workers expressed concerns about the potential impact of robots on the social wellbeing of care receivers (Bäcman et al., 2020; Turjamaa et al., 2023). The qualitative study by Turjamaa et al. (2023), for example, indicated that the introduction of medication management robots in older adults' homes prompted homecare workers to question whether reduced staff visits may increase loneliness (Turjamaa et al., 2023). However, some care receivers were also reported to express greater independence, noting that they could take responsibility for their medication (Turjamaa et al., 2023). In another study, the use of robotic shower support tools raised concerns about missed opportunities for social bonding between homecare workers and care receivers during caring routines (Bäcman et al., 2020). Although participants in the study did not report explicit experiences of isolation, the authors emphasised the perceived risk and

recommended considering these potential outcomes during the implementation process (Bäcman et al., 2020).

In contrast, several studies reported that robots, particularly during their initial introduction, prompted collaboration and were perceived as facilitators of social interactions (Hansen, 2015; Read et al., 2020). Collaboration was often linked to shared learning, the need to adapt team routines or troubleshoot technical problems, which created opportunities for informal knowledge sharing and teamwork (Barker & Jewitt, 2023; Beran et al., 2020; Lambrechts et al., 2021; Persson et al., 2023; Vogt & König, 2023; Wurhofer et al., 2015; Yuan et al., 2022).

In four studies across different domains, these collaborative learning processes were described as contributing to stronger social ties among workers, as groups gathered to exchange strategies, learn how the robot functioned and supported one another when addressing challenges (Barker & Jewitt, 2023; Lambrechts et al., 2021; Vogt & König, 2023; Wurhofer et al., 2015). Other studies illustrated similar dynamics. For example, the implementation of automated milking systems in Norway prompted dairy farmers to form new networks to share knowledge and assist each other with technical difficulties (Hansen, 2015). In dementia care settings, nurses engaged in mutual learning and knowledge exchange on how to best integrate robotic animals into patient care (Persson et al., 2023).

Robots introduced into healthcare practices were also described as catalysts for team-based learning. Physiotherapists, for example, framed exoskeleton training as a process of shared exploration (Read et al., 2020). In Beran et al.'s (2020) study of a paediatric hospital, a robot initially used by child-life specialists to relax and comfort children as well as enhance playfulness attracted interest from other departments. This curiosity led to increased collaboration and knowledge-sharing across departments as colleagues sought the expertise of the child-life specialists to utilise the robot in other situations (Beran et al., 2020).

3.2.3. Individual level: how do robots shape roles, skills, values and emotional responses at work?

The introduction of robots into workplaces has been described as reshaping job tasks across a variety of sectors, often requiring workers to take on new roles, responsibilities and forms of expertise, as illustrated in the following examples. In dairy farming, three studies reported shifts in daily routines following the adoption of robotic milking systems (Hansen, 2015; Lundström & Lindblom, 2021; Tse et al., 2018). Manual milking tasks were replaced by the need to monitor robotic systems and interpret automated data outputs. While some farmers appreciated the reduced physical strain and increased flexibility, others described feeling overwhelmed by the volume of data and reported a diminished sense of professional expertise and connection to their animals, as hands-on interaction gave way to data interpretation (Tse et al., 2018). Due to this increased focus on technology, some farmers expressed a sense of alienation from their profession (Hansen, 2015). Similarly, Laakso et al. (2023) observed that the roles of pharmacy staff were reconfigured, following the introduction of automated dispensing systems. Tasks once focused on preparing prescriptions were relocated to pharmacy robots, while staff increasingly took on customer service and over-the-counter sales. As a result, this development prompted workers to reskill in marketing and communication, as they navigated a transition from technical-medical work to more commercially oriented roles (Laakso et al., 2023).

While the study by Laakso et al. (2023) pointed to the need for workers to acquire new skills, other studies portray robots as supporting and enhancing existing expertise, especially in healthcare (Egido-García et al., 2020; Stephenson & Stephens, 2018). For example, robotic rehabilitation systems were seen to augment physiotherapists' work by performing repetitive tasks, allowing therapists to focus on other aspects of care (Stephenson & Stephens, 2018).

In contrast, studies involving assembly line workers (Chigbu & Nekhwevha, 2022; Ngcwangu, 2023; Schumacher et al., 2022; Wurhofer et al., 2015) and warehouse workers (Berkers et al., 2023) indicated that

workers often framed their experiences in terms of reduced autonomy, where work rhythms had to align with the operational logic of machines. Tasks were perceived as becoming more fragmented and repetitive, while complex tasks were often reallocated to higher-skilled operators. In such contexts, low-skilled workers reported concerns about fewer opportunities for skill development and diminished control over their work trajectories (Laakso et al., 2023; Lloyd & Payne, 2023; Nikolova et al., 2024).

The pursuit of increased efficiency and productivity was frequently cited as a rationale for robot implementation (Berkers et al., 2023; Chigbu & Nekhwevha, 2022). Perceived productivity gains have been reported in certain contexts, such as production line environments (Chigbu & Nekhwevha, 2022) and improved time management for caregivers (Law et al., 2021). However, the same study by Law et al. (2021) also highlighted how laboratory staff working with delivery robots expressed doubts about the benefits, instead raising concerns about robot reliability (Law et al., 2021). A survey of workers in robotised workplaces across various sectors in Finland, including industry, construction, healthcare, science, technology, retail, and business, also reported mixed responses. While around a quarter of respondents described their work as more engaging, another quarter reported no change, and the remaining half experienced their work as less engaging (Turja et al., 2024). In Chigbu and Nekhwevha's (2022) study set in the automotive industry, some workers described repetitive tasks as a source of pride and tangible contribution. When robots assumed these tasks on an assembly line, workers reflected on a sense of underutilisation and diminished engagement, which they associated with declining confidence and job satisfaction (Chigbu & Nekhwevha, 2022).

Beyond changes in task structures and skill shifts, several studies in healthcare and agriculture indicated that robots prompted workers to re-evaluate their professional values (Hansen, 2015; Mortenson et al., 2020; Perruchoud et al., 2023; Persson et al., 2023; Tuuli & Jaana, 2020; Yuan et al., 2022). These concerns were particularly prevalent in professions centred on human care and relationships, though not limited to them. In elder and dementia care, for example, ethical concerns included dignity, deception and the potential infantilisation of care home residents (Perruchoud et al., 2023; Persson et al., 2023; Tuuli & Jaana, 2020; Yuan et al., 2022). In two care home studies, caregivers described therapeutic benefits of robot animals while simultaneously expressing discomfort with the idea that residents might misinterpret the robots as real animals (Perruchoud et al., 2023; Persson et al., 2023). This raised questions about deception and the boundaries of relational care. Some participants suggested that ethical use could be supported through specialised training, experience exchange and regular evaluations (Perruchoud et al., 2023). Similarly, in other settings where robots were used for social or conversational purposes, caregivers questioned whether the use aligned with their role-specific values (Tuuli & Jaana, 2020). Additionally, other healthcare workers described that the integration of robots as affecting their perceived control over task execution and decision-making (Kang et al., 2016; Moloney et al., 2024; Mortenson et al., 2020; Read et al., 2020; Schuessler et al., 2020; Vogt & König, 2023; Şenol Çelik et al., 2024). For example, in Mortenson et al.'s (2020) physiotherapy study, some workers raised safety concerns regarding robotic-assisted rehabilitation. One physiotherapist opted out of training, citing fears that robotic malfunction could harm patients (Mortenson et al., 2020).

Workers' emotional responses to robot collaboration were described as complex. Across several domains, participants expressed excitement about learning new skills and using robots (Schuessler et al., 2020; Silveira Thomas Porto & Catal, 2021; Turjamaa et al., 2023). Some found satisfaction in interactions between robots and clients or customers, with staff reporting joy in witnessing positive reactions from residents in care homes (Yuan et al., 2022) and restaurant customers interacting with robots (Mejia et al., 2024). However, emotional responses to robot collaboration were also described as contradictory at times. Studies involving nurses in robotic-assisted surgery, for example, noted that

feelings of excitement and pride in using robotic-assisted surgery systems were frequently accompanied by experiences of increased workload and elevated stress (Kang et al., 2016; Şenol Çelik et al., 2024). These accounts reflect a broader tension: while robots may be associated with technological advancements, they can simultaneously introduce new demands on individual workers. For instance, practical limitations such as robot malfunctions and operational speed (Barker & Jewitt, 2023; Beran et al., 2020; Huisman & Kort, 2019; Law et al., 2021; Lim et al., 2024; Mejia et al., 2024) as well as limited functionality (Huisman & Kort, 2019; Vishwanath et al., 2019) were reported across several studies. In some cases, these challenges appeared to foster scepticism and reduce trust in robots' reliability (Barker & Jewitt, 2023; Mejia et al., 2024).

The mental and emotional implications of working with robots were explicitly addressed in four studies covering different industries, focusing on worker wellbeing (Chen & Cai, 2024; He et al., 2023; Stankevičiūtė et al., 2021; Yam et al., 2022). Their findings indicated that working with robots can lower workers' self-esteem, increase the risk of burnout (He et al., 2023), and heighten job insecurity, which, in turn, may contribute to stress, burnout, or intentions to leave the workplace (Chen & Cai, 2024). For instance, increased anxiety around job replacement was linked to declines in job performance (Stankevičiūtė et al., 2021), while concerns about social dynamics and fairness were associated with burnout and job incivility (Yam et al., 2022). Notably, the perception of robots as intelligent seemed to amplify these anxieties, particularly when workers believed robots were positioned at an advantage relative to humans (Chen & Cai, 2024). Yet in other instances, the same perception of robots as intelligent appeared to foster greater job satisfaction, particularly when the competence was interpreted as enhancing task outcomes (He et al., 2023).

4. Discussion

The purpose of this review was to explore how workers across diverse domains experience and interpret collaboration with robots. In addressing the first research question, our findings indicate that workers' experiences are heterogeneous and contextual, shaped by factors such as the degree of worker involvement, organisational clarity and the perceived impact on workers' skills and values. Interpretations range from optimistic narratives of augmentation to critical reflections on deskilling, control and alienation.

Across domains, robots entered the workplace in different functional roles, which conditioned both the reconfiguration of core tasks and workers' sensemaking. Given the uneven distribution of studies across sectors, our findings should be read as cross-cutting themes with domain-specific boundary conditions rather than as a basis for generalisation across industries. To navigate this complexity, the discussion is structured around three interconnected dimensions of influence: the organisational level (systemic structures), the team level (interpersonal dynamics) and the individual level (subjective meaning-making). These dimensions collectively reflect not only the technical realities but also social, emotional and ethical complexities of robot integration, as summarised in Table 4.

Each level is examined in turn, followed by a discussion of their combined impact and differences in worker experiences across professional domains, which addresses the second research question. Taken together, the findings challenge simplistic framings of human-robot collaboration as either empowering or displacing, instead revealing a nuanced spectrum of situated experiences shaped by context, roles and relationships.

4.1. Organisational level: how do organisational logics and practices configure workers' relations with robots?

Across studies, we observed the importance of involving workers in implementation processes. When the adoption of robots was perceived

Table 4

Overview of key dimensions, divided into levels, influence, dynamics and their overall descriptions.

LEVEL	INFLUENCE	DYNAMICS	DESCRIPTION
Organisational level	Systemic structures (policies, management decisions, organisational support)	Structural conditions (e.g. top-down decision-making)	This theme addresses how organisational structures and decisions shape the conditions under which workers encounter robots. It includes implementation strategies, training initiatives and communication approaches. These factors influence whether workers feel involved, supported or excluded from the process. It can affect their acceptance of and attitudes toward robots.
Team level	Interpersonal dynamics (how people relate to each other in presence of robot)	Relational interactions (e.g. negotiation of meaning with colleagues)	This theme focuses on how workers interact with each other in the presence of robots. Social dynamics between human workers may shift as robots either disrupt existing relationships (e.g. decreasing human-human collaborative tasks) or enable new forms of collaboration and gatherings (e.g. joint trouble-shooting or informal knowledge exchange).
Individual level	Worker in interaction with the robot (internal interpretations of how the individual experiences and processes change)	Subjective impact (e.g. effect on person's values, emotions or identity)	This theme captures how individual workers make sense of their changing roles in response to robot integration. It includes concerns related to skills, evolving job roles, autonomy, value tensions and mental health.

as top-down and opaque, workers expressed mistrust, resistance and reduced motivation (Huisman & Kort, 2019; Meissner et al., 2020; Wurhofer et al., 2015). This even led to the avoidance of robots (Vogt & König, 2023). Notably, many of the negative outcomes (e.g., confusion, uncertainty, anxiety about role displacement) were more a result of organisational failure to introduce robots in a transparent and inclusive manner than of the robots themselves (Huisman & Kort, 2019). These findings are consistent with previous research that has identified fears of redundancy and job replacement as significant concerns in robot adoption (e.g. Abeliansky et al., 2024; Fosch-Villaronga et al., 2020; Smids et al., 2020). This emphasises the need for clear communication about the purpose and scope of robot deployment. Making organisational intentions explicit can help workers understand why robots are introduced and how their roles might change.

Conversely, participatory strategies, such as co-design activities, open communication and hands-on training were associated with greater confidence and adaptability (Berkers et al., 2023). Participatory

formats for worker input are particularly recommended due to their potential to improve alignment between worker capabilities and robot functionalities (Arora & Garg, 2024; Dornelles et al., 2023; Hentout et al., 2019; Tuuli Turja, Minkkinen, & Mauno, 2022; Winkle et al., 2020). However, Sorell (2022) expresses concerns that, without careful attention to power dynamics and long-term implications, participation may legitimise changes that undermine workers' future roles and risk the creation of workplaces without them (Sorell, 2022). Similarly, Lee (2024) highlights that participatory processes can reveal conflicting perspectives among workers, and achieving consensus is not always possible (Lee, 2024).

4.2. Team level: how do human-robot relations emerge and evolve in collaborative team contexts?

Team-level dynamics revealed ambivalent findings. While some workers reported concerns regarding the loss of informal social interactions, particularly in caregiving or service-oriented roles (Bäcckman et al., 2020; Turjamaa et al., 2023), other studies observed increased teamwork during the initial phases of robot integration (Barker & Jewitt, 2023; Read et al., 2020). In these cases, robots enabled mutual learning (Read et al., 2020), peer support (Hansen, 2015) and cross-departmental exchange (Beran et al., 2020). These findings underscore that interpersonal relations and human-human interactions remain crucial for worker well-being and job satisfaction, aligning with broader literature on the social context of work as a contributor to perceived purpose (Wrzesniewski et al., 2003).

Beyond human-human dynamics, the interaction characteristics and qualities between human workers and robots significantly influenced the experience, even if the explicit concept of 'human-robot teaming' was not always central to the reviewed studies. For instance, a recent study found that interactions characterised by mutual support and balanced human-robot collaboration contributed to positive user experiences, enhanced levels of trust, and greater fluency in collaboration (Nenna et al., 2025). This aligns with a broader tendency to anthropomorphise robots, which can foster greater comfort and engagement with robots (de Graaf et al., 2015; Dörrenbächer et al., 2022; Sauppé & Mutlu, 2015). However, this attribution of sociality is not universally positive. Negative perceptions, particularly when workers experience recurring negative interactions with robots, can reinforce negative attitudes (Saadon et al., 2025). Moreover, other studies indicate that robots cannot offer the same level and quality of social encounters as other humans (Lim et al., 2024; Paluch et al., 2022). This aligns with the review by Wullenkord and Eysel (2020) that states that robots "can only simulate a connection that resembles a human-human relations" (Wullenkord & Eysel, 2020, p. 87). Our findings reveal a relational shift that calls for thoughtful design of team processes, communication and support structures that respect the human dimensions of collaborative work.

4.3. Individual level: how do robots shape roles, skills, values and emotional relations at work?

At the individual level, workers responded to robot integration with a wide range of emotions and reflections. For some, robots were perceived as enhancing professional capabilities and fostering skill development (Egido-García et al., 2020; Stephenson & Stephens, 2018). For others, especially those in repetitive or routinised roles, robots signalled a threat to autonomy, job satisfaction and sense of pride in their work (Chigbu & Nekhwevha, 2022; Ngcwangu, 2023; Wurhofer et al., 2015). This reflects the differential impact of robot implementation across professional domains, where the nature of the work significantly mediates individual experience.

Beyond direct job-related impacts, robot integration often raised ethical considerations around human-robot collaboration, emphasising the heightened importance of human-centric qualities in the workplace.

Conflicting professional values emerged as workers navigated role re-definitions and their implications for professional identity (Lundström & Lindblom, 2021; Persson et al., 2023; Read et al., 2020; Yuan et al., 2022). These anxieties often extended beyond personal impact, as workers expressed concern for others influenced by their work, such as care home residents, patients or customers. In these cases, ethical reflections were tied to professional values, such as emotional labour (Tuuli & Jaana, 2020), empathy (Turjamaa et al., 2023) and human dignity (Perruchoud et al., 2023; Persson et al., 2023). This corresponds with broader calls in the human-robot interaction literature to recognise and address societal and ethical issues, including potential risks for vulnerable groups (Winkle et al., 2023; Wullenkord & Eyszel, 2020). Furthermore, the mental health implications of robot deployment, particularly for vulnerable groups such as workers close to retirement or in low-skilled jobs, underscore the need to acknowledge and mitigate potential negative psychological impacts in human-robot interaction research, robot development and deployment (Abeliansky et al., 2024).

4.4. Profession-specific variations of human-robot collaboration

The second research question concerned variations of human-robot collaboration across domains. The demand-control-support model, developed by Karasek and Theorell (1990), can help to further understand the varying impact on work domains. This model considers the interplay of demands (e.g. workload, task difficulty), control (decision latitude, skill development) and support (aid from colleagues and management), offering insights into how robot integration configures an individual's work situation (Karasek & Theorell, 1990). Across the reviewed studies, indicators of demands, control and support were frequently reported, albeit not always explicitly framed in these terms, allowing the demand-control-support model to serve as a sensitising framework for cross-domain comparison.

Our results point to two main aspects that influenced variation: the control that workers have over the utilisation of robots in their work, and the impact robots have on their core tasks. Importantly, these aspects cut across sectors and robot types. These were used as axes in Fig. 5 to visualise our interpretation of the varying impact of robots on job roles across professions. The positioning of professions and representative cases from the reviewed literature should be understood as an

interpretive synthesis rather than a strict classification. The clusters reflect recurring patterns identified across multiple studies, based on reported levels of worker autonomy, perceived task transformation and involvement in implementation.

In contexts, such as physiotherapy or dementia care, robotic devices were introduced as optional resources that workers could integrate into their practice when suitable (Beran et al., 2020; Stephenson & Stephens, 2018). These workers maintained high levels of control over the application of robots and thus, robots functioned as extensions of professional practice, offering additional support without disrupting existing routines or changing demands. These examples are found in the high-control, low-impact cluster in Fig. 5.

In contrast, placed on the low-control and high-impact cluster in Fig. 5, professions such as robotic-assisted surgery nurses (Schuessler et al., 2020; Şenol Çelik et al., 2024) or assembly line workers (Chigbu & Nekhwevha, 2022; Ngcwangu, 2023) experienced more far-reaching changes that entailed restructuring of tasks and workflows or new dependencies on automation. In these cases, work demands often increased while worker control decreased, and this was frequently accompanied by limited support (e.g., inadequate training initiatives).

Another pattern is characterised by medium levels of changing work tasks, with some flexibility in how and when to apply robots. In this category, cases included self-organised initiatives to improve their practice and enhance their knowledge, for instance, in care home settings (Yuan et al., 2022) and among hotel staff (Liu et al., 2024). In these cases, groups of co-workers gathered to learn about the robot and jointly explore how to use it efficiently in their context. The demand for further knowledge was addressed through worker-led initiatives in the absence of organisational support. This can be seen as an example of coping strategies. In other cases, for example, in the high-control and low-impact cluster, workers were primarily concerned with ethical aspects. In contrast, cases in the low-control and high-impact cluster raised questions about training and job security. For assembly line workers, information and inclusion in the decision-making process of the reorganisation of work practices were seen as crucial, as their employment depended on them. These fears of job replacement were not shared by all occupational groups in the same cluster. Conversely, for robot-assisted surgery (RAS) nurses, job security was secondary to concerns regarding specialised and relevant training. This was seen as important

Fig. 5. Interpretation of how robots impact workers' tasks and workers' perceived levels of control.

in order to accurately perform their changing tasks and fulfil new demands on their roles.

These patterns suggest that organisational strategies for implementing and deploying robots play a central role in shaping workers' responses to them, often more decisively than the systems' technical characteristics.

4.5. Implications for theory, design and practice

This section first outlines the theoretical contributions of this literature review and then presents recommendations that guide managers, designers, developers and workers seeking to integrate robots in ways that support work practices and workers' well-being.

Fig. 6. Interrelatedness of the analytical levels.

4.5.1. Theoretical implications

This review shows that the deployment and implementation of robots in workplaces encompasses more than technical integration and workflow optimisation. It emphasises the importance of integrating and acknowledging emotional and relational dimensions in the workplace that influence the acceptance and utilisation of robots. This builds on the growing body of literature which highlights human factors and recognises human-robot collaboration as a sociotechnical practice (e.g., (Apraiz et al., 2023; Baltrusch et al., 2022; Berx et al., 2025; Dörrenbächer et al., 2022; Sorell, 2022)). These studies provide deeper insights into improving the user experience of working alongside robots (Apraiz et al., 2023), and addressing workers' safety and well-being (Berx et al., 2025). They also explore how robot capabilities could be developed to support more meaningful forms of interaction in the workplace and other settings (Dörrenbächer et al., 2022). While these studies demonstrate the importance of human factors, they do not yet integrate how these experiences are shaped across different levels of work organisation. This review contributes to theory by conceptualising human-robot collaboration as a multi-level sociotechnical system in which organisational structures, team practices, and individual meaning-making shape the integration of robots into work. These levels should not be regarded in isolation, but rather as a system in which the three levels are interconnected and influence each other, as illustrated by Fig. 6.

The framework highlights that organisational structures and decisions regarding robot implementation and deployment at the organisational level significantly shape conditions and processes at the team level, which, in turn, directly impact individual workers' experiences and meaning-making in relation to robots (Fig. 6, A). Conversely, individual and team-level interactions and adaptations affect organisational practices, indicating a dynamic relationship between these analytical levels (Fig. 6, B). Moreover, the interpersonal interaction between co-workers who work alongside robots appears to be a significant factor, as it has been identified as a factor influencing individual workers' sense of companionship and belonging. Consequently, the actions and behaviours of individual workers, as they relate to team dynamics, directly impact the team's overall experience (Fig. 6, C).

This implies that organisational structures and decisions regarding the deployment, implementation, and utilisation of robots significantly influence workers' acceptance and motivation to work with robots. They also influence the extent to which workers exercise control over the utilisation of robots, as well as the degree to which roles and work tasks are subject to change (as illustrated in Fig. 5). For example, the impact of robots on the roles of physiotherapists can be described as relatively low. Physiotherapists have the option of utilising robots as a supplementary resource alongside others. In contrast, workers in assembly lines or warehouses are highly impacted in their daily work and have low autonomy in deciding when and how to use robots. Consistent with the concept of technologies-in-practice (Orlikowski, 2000), these examples illustrate that the experience of working with robots is highly context-dependent, shaped not only by technology itself but also by organisational structures, autonomy and work practices. This underscores considerable variations across work settings and underscores the need for further research into how human-robot collaboration is enacted in practice.

Workers in lower-skilled or more routinised roles appeared especially vulnerable to having tasks restructured or downgraded, with limited say in how robots were deployed (Berkers et al., 2023; Laakso et al., 2023; Nikolova et al., 2024). In many cases, the integration process was driven primarily by managerial or technical priorities, rather than by consultation with those directly affected. Examining these power structures provides critical insight into how robot integration redefines interactions and roles, particularly across different professional groups involved in the process, a perspective aligned with Winkle et al. (2023)'s call for a more ethical, practical approach to human-robot interaction.

Furthermore, attitudes towards robots are not static, but evolve over time. This raises questions about the future of work: Which tasks should be delegated to robots? Who gets to decide? What values should inform these decisions? The common narrative of delegating dirty, dull or dangerous tasks assumes a shared definition of undesirable work, but such tasks may hold meaning or provide a sense of pride for some workers (Chigbu & Nekhwevha, 2022; van der Deijl, 2024). Similarly, Baltrusch et al. (2022) argue that the question is not whether human-robot collaboration should occur, but how it can be designed to enhance conditions and aspects for human workers (Baltrusch et al., 2022). This shifts the theoretical focus of human-robot collaboration from efficiency and task optimisation to the meaningful integration of robots, ensuring that they are valuable and sustainable for both organisations and their workforces.

4.5.2. Implications for design and practice

Based on the findings of this review, these implications can provide concrete recommendations and inspiration for management, designers, developers, and workers.

Our findings show that experiences of human-robot collaboration varied with workers' control over robot use and the extent of task and workflow reconfigurations. Actively engaging employees in the design and implementation process may not only build trust and acceptance but also help shape and refine robot functionalities and use cases. Such involvement can reveal new opportunities and constraints in applying and deploying robots, ensuring alignment with organisational goals and leveraging workers' expertise. Clear procedures for gathering, tracking, and acting on feedback help ensure that workers' input is not solely symbolic but actually informs decisions.

Training initiatives can serve as an opportunity to address two kinds of "how to work with a robot". First, providing training on technical knowledge, and second, ensuring that the integration fits into the work culture and its work routines. To suit different contexts, needs, and learning styles, training opportunities can include a range of formats (e.g., formal sessions, hands-on practice) as well as informal opportunities for experimentation and familiarisation with robots. Creating forums for asking questions and exchanging experiences can further encourage learning, collaboration, and confidence. Management, in collaboration with HR or training specialists, can regularly evaluate if existing goals, materials, and resources remain appropriate as needs evolve.

An important finding from this review was the significance of social interactions for workers. Designers and developers could therefore explore how the robots' potential as facilitators of social interactions could be translated into their design. This could affect both the robot's features and its deployment in the work context to leverage human-human exchanges.

By applying comprehensive testing throughout the robot design process, considering ethical aspects, designers can reduce potential misunderstandings or unintended cases of deception. This can further be extended to address ethical considerations that influence outcomes not only for workers but also for secondary groups affected by human-robot collaboration, such as patients or clients.

Eventually, the implications for workers concern how to relate to robots in their roles and how to address ethical considerations in daily work. An evaluation of how robots may fit into an individual's responsibilities, while also considering professional values and ethical boundaries, can help define the cases and limits of robot use in practice. This process of reflection might also identify cases or situations where robot involvement may be considered inappropriate or undesirable.

To summarise, these implications underline the importance of integrating robots in ways that respect existing work practices, support workers' well-being, and address ethical concerns. By systematically considering structures, team routines, and individual concerns, organisations, designers, and workers can increase the likelihood that robots are integrated in ways that support human-robot collaboration, protect workers' well-being, and address ethical responsibilities towards

patients, clients, and other stakeholders.

4.6. Limitations and future research

This review has several limitations. It focused on physically embodied robots, which means that the rapidly evolving impacts of generative AI and autonomous digital agents were not included, representing a potential field for future exploration. While the included studies span various domains, we observed an uneven sector distribution in the evidence base with an overrepresentation of studies in the healthcare sector. Other sectors, such as the creative industries remain underrepresented. Sampling across domains offers a broad picture of how workers in different industries are affected by experience and perceive working with robots, revealing both commonalities and differences across fields. However, we also acknowledge that the reviewed collection of studies only provides insights into the selected industries and robot types and cannot support universal generalisation about working with robots and warrant further investigation in future research. All studies were conducted in industrialised countries, limiting insight into how human-robot collaboration unfolds in emerging and developing economies. Additionally, many studies were short-term or lacked a specified duration, restricting our understanding of how worker experiences evolve over time.

Future research should consider longitudinal designs to capture the dynamic nature of human-robot collaboration and its long-term impact on skills, wellbeing and organisational practices across different professions, for example, in the contexts of education, entertainment and the creative industries. Considering other cultural settings outside industrialised nations could offer an additional perspective for comparing and adjusting the implementation for these specific environments. Furthermore, future studies could explore how power dynamics shape implementation processes and how different participatory design approaches influence organisational conditions in ways that support both institutional goals and worker needs.

5. Conclusions

The aim of this review was to synthesise how workers across multiple domains experience and interpret collaboration with robots. By analysing 44 empirical studies, the review highlighted a spectrum of situated, context-dependent experiences that move beyond framings of work robotisation as either empowering or displacing.

By presenting the findings across three interrelated levels (organisational, team, and individual), specific aspects of organisational structures, interpersonal relations, and individual sense-making in working with robots were highlighted. Findings show that organisational conditions, most prominently implementation strategies but also involvement in decision-making processes, management communication style and training initiatives, strongly shaped how workers engage with robots. At the team level, robot integration was associated with changes in interpersonal dynamics, sometimes disrupting informal interactions, but also enabling new forms of collaboration. The influence of robots on social interactions was particularly noted. While none of the studies reported actual decreases in social interactions, concerns about these consequences were raised across multiple domains. On the individual level, workers navigate role redefinitions, emotional responses and professional values, revealing how robots not only affect tasks, but also identities and ethical commitments.

Together, these insights revealed that work domains are impacted by robots in varying degrees. While some professions reported only minor modifications, others were undergoing profound changes. This, in turn, influences how different worker groups perceive and respond to the implementation of robots. Mechanisms were defined as the level of control workers held and the level of change in core tasks.

Finally, our findings underline the importance of designing human-robot collaboration not only around efficiency, but around workers'

social and emotional realities. Evaluating and addressing power relations, professional norms and long-term adaptation can help shape future workplaces that are both technologically and socially sustainable.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Sarah Skavron: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Günter Alce:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Björn Fischer:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Susanne Frennert:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Ethical approval statement

Ethical approval was not required for this study as it is based exclusively on the analysis of previously published literature and did not involve any new collection of data from human or animal subjects.

Declaration on informed consent

Informed consent was not required for this study because no new data were collected from human participants.

Use of generative AI

During the preparation of this work the first author used DeepL Write, OpenAI ChatGPT and Grammarly in order to edit and improve the clarity of parts of the manuscript. After using these tools, the first author reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chbah.2026.100275>.

References

- Abeliansky, A. L., Beulmann, M., & Prettnner, K. (2024). Are they coming for us? Industrial robots and the mental health of workers. *Research Policy*, 53(3), Article 104956. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2024.104956>
- Apraiz, A., Lasa, G., & Mazmela, M. (2023). Evaluation of user experience in human-robot interaction: A systematic literature review. *International Journal of Social Robotics*, 15(2), 187–210. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12369-022-00957-z>
- Arora, N., & Garg, N. (2024). Meaningful work in the digital Age- A comprehensive review and framework. *Human Resource Development International*, 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13678868.2024.2336866>
- Bäckman, C., Bergkvist, L., & Kristensson, P. (2020). Elderly and care personnel's user experiences of a robotic shower [Article] *Journal of Enabling Technologies*, 14(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JET-07-2019-0033>
- Baltrusch, S. J., Krause, F., de Vries, A. W., van Dijk, W., & de Looze, M. P. (2022). What about the human in human robot collaboration? *Ergonomics*, 65(5), 719–740. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00140139.2021.1984585>

- Barker, N., & Jewitt, C. (2023). Collaborative robots and tangled passages of tactile-affects [Article] *ACM Transactions on Interactive Intelligent Systems*, 12(2), Article 3534090. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3534090>.
- Beran, T., Pearson, J. R., Lashewicz, B., & Baggott, S. (2020). Perspectives of child life specialists after many years of working with a humanoid robot in a pediatric hospital: Narrative design [Article] *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 22(11), Article e23496. <https://doi.org/10.2196/23496>.
- Berkers, H. A., Rispens, S., & Le Blanc, P. M. (2023). The role of robotization in work design: A comparative case study among logistic warehouses. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 34(9), 1852–1875. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2022.2043925>
- Berx, N., Decré, W., De Schutter, J., & Pintelon, L. (2025). A harmonious synergy between robotic performance and well-being in human-robot collaboration: A vision and key recommendations. *Annual Reviews in Control*, 59, Article 100984. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arconrol.2024.100984>
- Bijker, W., & Pinch, T. (1987). The social construction of facts and artifacts: Or how the sociology of science and the sociology of technology might benefit each other. 14, 17–50.
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp0630a>
- Callari, T. C., Curzi, Y., & Lohse, N. (2025). Realising human-robot collaboration in manufacturing? A journey towards industry 5.0 amid organisational paradoxical tensions. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 219, Article 124249. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2025.124249>
- Carissoli, C., Negri, L., Bassi, M., Storm, F. A., & Delle Fave, A. (2024). Mental workload and human-robot interaction in collaborative tasks: A scoping review. *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*, 40(20), 6458–6477. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10447318.2023.2254639>
- Chen, C. C., & Cai, R. (2024). Are robots stealing our jobs? Examining robot-phobia as a job stressor in the hospitality workplace. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCHM-09-2023-1454>
- Chigbu, B. I., & Nekhwevha, F. H. (2022). The collaborative work experience of robotics and human workers in the automobile industry in South Africa [Article] *African Journal of Science, Technology, Innovation & Development*, 14(1), 280–287. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20421338.2020.1837446>.
- de Graaf, M. M. A., Allouch, S. B., & Klamer, T. (2015). Sharing a life with Harvey: Exploring the acceptance and relationship-building with a social robot. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 43, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2014.10.030>
- Dornelles, J. d. A., Ayala, N. F., & Frank, A. G. (2023). Collaborative or substitutive robots? Effects on workers' skills in manufacturing activities. *International Journal of Production Research*, 61(22), 7922–7955. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2023.2240912>
- Dörrenbächer, J., Ringfort-Felner, R., Neuhaus, R., & Hassenzahl, M. (2022). *Meaningful futures with robots: Designing a new coexistence*. CRC Press.
- Egido-García, V., Estévez, D., Corrales-Paredes, A., Terrón-López, M. J., & Velasco-Quintana, P. J. (2020). Integration of a social robot in a pedagogical and logopedic intervention with children: A case study [Article] *Sensors*, 20(22), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s20226483>. Article 6483.
- Elias, A., Trigo, M. J. G., & Camacho-Villa, C. (2025). Analyzing previous human-robot interaction implementation in agriculture: What can we learn from the past?. In *Proceedings of the 2025 ACM/IEEE international conference on human-robot interaction*. Melbourne, Australia.
- Eurofound. (2024). *Human-robot interaction: What changes in the workplace?* L. Publications Office of the European Union.
- Fosch-Villaronga, E., Lutz, C., & Tamò-Larriex, A. (2020). Gathering expert opinions for social robots' ethical, legal, and societal concerns: Findings from four international workshops. *International Journal of Social Robotics*, 12(2), 441–458. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12369-019-00605-z>
- Gammarano, R. (2019). *Work and employment are not synonyms*. International Labour Organization ILOSTAT. Retrieved 03 April 2025 from <https://ilostat.ilo.org/blog/work-and-employment-are-not-synonyms/>.
- Graneheim, U. H., Lindgren, B.-M., & Lundman, B. (2017). Methodological challenges in qualitative content analysis: A discussion paper. *Nurse Education Today*, 56, 29–34. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2017.06.002>
- Gualtieri, L., Rauch, E., & Vidoni, R. (2021). Emerging research fields in safety and ergonomics in industrial collaborative robotics: A systematic literature review. *Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing*, 67, 101998. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rcim.2020.101998>.
- Hansen, B. G. (2015). Robotic milking-farmer experiences and adoption rate in Jæren, Norway [Article] *Journal of Rural Studies*, 41, 109–117. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2015.08.004>.
- He, G. H., Zheng, X. N., Li, W. P., Zheng, L. X., & He, Y. F. (2023). The dark side of employee collaboration with robots: Exploring its impact on self-esteem threat and burnout. *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10447318.2023.2295691>
- Hentout, A., Aouache, M., Maoudj, A., & Akli, I. (2019). Human-robot interaction in industrial collaborative robotics: A literature review of the decade 2008–2017. *Advanced Robotics*, 33(15-16), 764–799. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01691864.2019.1636714>
- Huisman, C., & Kort, H. (2019). Two-year use of care robot zora in dutch nursing homes: An evaluation study [Article] *Healthcare (Switzerland)*, 7(1), Article 31. <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare7010031>.
- Kang, M. J., De Gagne, J. C., & Kang, H. S. (2016). Perioperative nurses' work experience with robotic surgery: A focus group study [Article] *CIN: Computers, Informatics, Nursing*, 34(4), 152–158. <https://doi.org/10.1097/CIN.0000000000000224>.
- Laakso, K. A., Turja, T., & Särkikoski, T. (2023). Multi-faceted boundary relations in pharmacy automation. *International Journal of Healthcare Technology and Management*, 20(4), 326–347. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJHTM.2023.134446>
- Lambrechts, W., Klaver, J. S., Koudijzer, L., & Semeijn, J. (2021). Human factors influencing the implementation of cobots in high volume distribution centres. *Logist*, 5(2). <https://doi.org/10.3390/logistics5020032>
- Latour, B. (1999). On recalling ANT. *The Sociological Review*, 47(1 suppl), 15–25.
- Law, M., Ahn, H. S., Broadbent, E., Peri, K., Kerse, N., Topou, E., Gasteiger, N., & MacDonald, B. (2021). Case studies on the usability, acceptability and functionality of autonomous mobile delivery robots in real-world healthcare settings [Article] *Intelligent service robotics*, 14(3), 387–398. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11370-021-00368-5>.
- Lee, H. R. (2024). Contrasting perspectives of workers: Exploring labor relations in workplace automation and potential interventions. In *Proceedings of the 2024 CHI conference on human factors in computing systems*. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3613904.3642907>. Honolulu, HI, USA.
- Lim, Y. W., Tan, S. W., Tan, C. Y. B., Lee, D. H. M., Siow, W. T., Heng, D. G. N., Mukhopadhyay, A., Lim, J. C., Sivasdas, S., Teo, E. L. K., Ho, L. K. Y., & Phua, J. (2024). An assessment of an inpatient robotic nurse assistant: A mixed-method study [Article] *Journal of Medical Systems*, 48(1), Article 99. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10916-024-02117-4>.
- Liu, X., Zhang, L., Xie, L., & Guan, X. (2024). What happens after the arrival of service robots? Investigating how robotic usage experience facilitates employees' exploitative and exploratory learning behaviors [Article] *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 123, Article 103936. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2024.103936>.
- Lloyd, C., & Payne, J. (2023). Digital skills in context: Working with robots in lower-skilled jobs [Article] *Economic and Industrial Democracy*, 44(4), 1084–1104. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0143831X22111416>.
- Lundström, C., & Lindblom, J. (2021). Care in dairy farming with automatic milking systems, identified using an activity theory lens [Article] *Journal of Rural Studies*, 87, 386–403. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2021.09.006>.
- Ma, L. M., Ijtsma, M., Feigh, K. M., & Pritchett, A. R. (2022). Metrics for human-robot team design: A teamwork perspective on evaluation of human-robot teams. *J. Hum.-Robot Interact.*, 11(3), Article 30. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3522581>
- Meissner, A., Trübsetz, A., Conti-Kufner, A. S., & Schmidler, J. (2020). Friend or foe understanding assembly workers' acceptance of human-robot collaboration [Article] *ACM Transactions on Human-Robot Interaction*, 10(1), Article 3394287 <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85095743307&partnerID=40&m-d5=9c2b277e0088b09d8fd4c59ea7d04ca2>.
- Mejia, C., Crandell, H. A., Broker, E., & Shoss, M. (2024). Working with service robots in the dining room: Employees' perspectives and realities [Article] *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Technology*, 15(5), 878–896. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JHTT-12-2023-0420>.
- Moloney, R., Coffey, A., Coffey, J. C., & Brien, B. O. (2024). Nurses' experiences of working with robotic assisted surgery in an Irish healthcare setting: A qualitative descriptive design [Article] *Nurse Education in Practice*, 81, Article 104183. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2024.104183>.
- Mortenson, W. B., Pysklywec, A., Chau, L., Prescott, M., & Townson, A. (2020). Therapists' experience of training and implementing an exoskeleton in a rehabilitation centre [Article] *Disability & Rehabilitation*, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09638288.2020.1789765>.
- Nenna, F., Orlando, E. M., Zanardi, D., Buodo, G., & Gamberini, L. (2025). Who is supporting whom? Balanced and unbalanced support perceptions shaping acceptance of collaborative robots. In *Proceedings of the 2025 ACM/IEEE international conference on human-robot interaction*. Melbourne, Australia.
- Ngwangu, S. (2023). Skill and deskilling in two automotive assembly plants in South Africa [Article] *Qualitative Sociology Review*, 19(1), 102–121. <https://doi.org/10.18778/1733-8077.19.1.05>.
- Nikolova, M., Cnossen, F., & Nikolaev, B. (2024). Robots, meaning, and self-determination [Article] *Research Policy*, 53(5), Article 104987. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2024.104987>.
- Orlikowski, J. W. (2000). Using technology and constituting structures: A practice lens for studying technology in organizations. *Organization Science*, 11(4), 404–428. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/2640412>.
- Paluch, S., Tuzovic, S., Holz, H. F., Kies, A., & Jörling, M. (2022). "My colleague is a robot" – exploring frontline employees' willingness to work with collaborative service robots. *Journal of Service Management*, 33(2), 363–388. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JOSM-11-2020-0406>
- Panagou, S., Neumann, W. P., & Fruggiero, F. (2024). A scoping review of human robot interaction research towards Industry 5.0 human-centric workplaces. *International Journal of Production Research*, 62(3), 974–990. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2023.2172473>.
- Perruchoud, S., Banwell, N., Jox, R. R., & Eggert, N. (2023). Social robots in care homes in French-speaking Switzerland: A qualitative and reflective study [Article] *Ethics, Medicine and Public Health*, 29, Article 100918. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jemep.2023.100918>.
- Persson, M., Ferm, L., Redmalm, D., & Iversen, C. (2023). Working with robotic animals in dementia care: The significance of caregivers' competences [Article] *Nordic Journal of Working Life Studies*, 13(3), 49–69. <https://doi.org/10.18291/njwls.136521>.
- Read, E., Woolsey, C., McGibbon, C. A., & O'Connell, C. (2020). Physiotherapists' experiences using the exo Bionic Exoskeleton with patients in a neurological rehabilitation Hospital: A qualitative study [Article] *Rehabilitation Research and Practice*, 2020, Article 2939573. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/2939573>.

- Romero, D., Stahre, J., Wuest, T., Noran, O., Bernus, P., Fasth, F.-B.Å., & Gorecky, D. (2016). *Towards an operator 4.0 typology: A human-centric perspective on the fourth industrial revolution technologies*.
- Saadon, N. H., Megidish, B., & Erel, H. (2025). Scammed by robots: Can deception by two simple non-humanoid robots shape general attitudes toward robots?. In *Proceedings of the 2025 ACM/IEEE international conference on human-robot interaction*. Melbourne, Australia.
- Sadeghian, S., & Hassenzähl, M. (2022). The "Artificial" colleague: Evaluation of work satisfaction. In *Collaboration with non-human coworkers proceedings of the 27th international conference on intelligent user interfaces*. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3490099.3511128>. Helsinki, Finland.
- Sartori, L., & Theodorou, A. (2022). A sociotechnical perspective for the future of AI: Narratives, inequalities, and human control. *Ethics and Information Technology*, 24(1), 4. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10676-022-09624-3>
- Sauppe, A., & Mutlu, B. (2015). The social impact of a robot Co-Worker in industrial settings. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2702123.2702181>.
- Schmidler, J., Knott, V., Hoelzel, C., & Bengler, K. (2015). Human Centered Assistance Applications for the working environment of the future. *Occupational Ergonomics*, 12, 83–95. <https://doi.org/10.3233/OER-150226>
- Schuessler, Z., Scott Stiles, A., & Mancuso, P. (2020). Perceptions and experiences of perioperative nurses and nurse anaesthetists in robotic-assisted surgery [Article] *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, 29(1-2), 60–74. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jocn.15053>.
- Schumacher, S., Hall, R., Waldman-Brown, A., & Sanneman, L. (2022). *Technology adoption of collaborative robots for welding in small and medium-sized enterprises: A case Study analysis*.
- Şenol Çelik, S., Tunçbilek, Z., Sarıköse, S., Topaktaş, G., & Canda, A. E. (2024). Roles, experience and views of nurses working in robotic surgery settings: A mixed-methods study [Article] *Journal of Perioperative Practice*, 34(7-8), 248–256. <https://doi.org/10.1177/17504589241231100>.
- Silveira Thomas Porto, C., & Catal, E. (2021). A comparative study of the opinions, experiences and individual innovativeness characteristics of operating room nurses on robotic surgery [Article] *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 77(12), 4755–4767. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jan.15020>.
- Simões, A. C., Pinto, A., Santos, J., Pinheiro, S., & Romero, D. (2022). *Designing human-robot collaboration (HRC) workspaces in industrial settings: A systemic literature review* (Vol. 62, pp. 28–43). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmsy.2021.11.007>
- Simone, V. D., Pasquale, V. D., Giubileo, V., & Miranda, S. (2022). Human-Robot Collaboration: An analysis of worker's performance. *Procedia Computer Science*, 200, 1540–1549. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2022.01.355>
- Smids, J., Nyholm, S., & Berkers, H. (2020). Robots in the workplace: A threat to—or opportunity for—Meaningful work? *Philosophy & Technology*, 33(3), 503–522. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13347-019-00377-4>
- Sorell, T. (2022). Cobots, "co-operation" and the replacement of human skill. *Ethics and Information Technology*, 24(4). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10676-022-09667-6>
- Stankevičiūtė, Ž., Staniškienė, E., & Ramanaukaitė, J. (2021). The impact of job insecurity on employee happiness at work: A case of robotised production line operators in furniture industry in Lithuania [Article] *Sustainability*, 13(3), 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13031563>. Article 1563.
- Stephenson, A., & Stephens, J. (2018). An exploration of physiotherapists' experiences of robotic therapy in upper limb rehabilitation within a stroke rehabilitation centre [Article] *Disability and Rehabilitation: Assistive Technology*, 13(3), 245–252. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17483107.2017.1306593>.
- Tsai, C.-Y., Marshall, J. D., Choudhury, A., Serban, A., Tsung-Yu Hou, Y., Jung, M. F., Dionne, S. D., & Yammarino, F. J. (2022). Human-robot collaboration: A multilevel and integrated leadership framework. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 33(1), Article 101594. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.leaqua.2021.101594>
- Tse, C., Barkema, H. W., DeVries, T. J., Rushen, J., Vasseur, E., & Pajor, E. A. (2018). Producer experience with transitioning to automatic milking: Cow training, challenges, and effect on quality of life [Article] *Journal of Dairy Science*, 101(10), 9599–9607. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2018-14662>.
- Turja, T., Minkkinen, J., & Mauno, S. (2022a). Robotizing meaningful work. *Journal of Information, Communication and Ethics in Society*, 20(2), 177–192. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JICES-06-2021-0063>
- Turja, T., Särkikoski, T., Koistinen, P., Krutova, O., & Melin, H. (2024). Job well robotized! – Maintaining task diversity and well-being in managing technological changes. *European Management Journal*, 42(1), 67–75. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.emj.2022.08.002>
- Turja, T., Särkikoski, T., Koistinen, P., & Melin, H. (2022b). Basic human needs and robotization: How to make deployment of robots worthwhile for everyone? [Article] *Technology in Society*, 68, Article 101917. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2022.101917>.
- Turjamaa, R., Vaismoradi, M., Kajander-Unkuri, S., & Kangasniemi, M. (2023). Home care professionals' experiences of successful implementation, use and competence needs of robot for medication management in Finland [Article] *Nursing Open*, 10(4), 2088–2097. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nop2.1456>.
- Tuuli, T., & Jaana, P. (2020). *The use of affective care robots calls forth value-based consideration*.
- Vishwanath, A., Singh, A., Chua, Y. H. V., Dauwels, J., & Magnenat-Thalmann, N. (2019). Humanoid co-workers: How is it like to work with a robot?. In *2019 28th IEEE international conference on robot and human interactive communication (RO-MAN)*.
- Vogt, G., & König, A. S. L. (2023). Robotic devices and ICT in long-term care in Japan: Their potential and limitations from a workplace perspective [Article] *Contemporary Japan*, 35(2), 270–290. <https://doi.org/10.1080/18692729.2021.2015846>.
- Weiss, A., Wortmeier, A. K., & Kubicek, B. (2021). Cobots in industry 4.0: A roadmap for future practice studies on human–robot Collaboration. *IEEE Transactions on Human-Machine Systems*, 51(4), 335–345. <https://doi.org/10.1109/THMS.2021.3092684>
- Welfare, K. S., Hallowell, M. R., Shah, J. A., & Riek, L. D. (2019). *Consider the human work experience when integrating robotics in the workplace*.
- Winkle, K., Caleb-Solly, P., Turton, A., & Bremner, P. (2020). Mutual shaping in the design of socially assistive robots: A case Study on social robots for therapy. *International Journal of Social Robotics*, 12(4), 847–866. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12369-019-00536-9>
- Winkle, K., McMillan, D., Arnelid, M., Harrison, K., Balaam, M., Johnson, E., & Leite, I. (2023). Feminist human-robot interaction: Disentangling power, principles and practice for better. In *More ethical HRI proceedings of the 2023 ACM/IEEE international conference on human-robot interaction*. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3568162.3576973>. Stockholm, Sweden.
- Wrzesniewski, A., Dutton, J. E., & Debebe, G. (2003). Interpersonal sensemaking and the meaning of work. *Research in Organizational Behavior*, 25, 93–135. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0191-3085\(03\)25003-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0191-3085(03)25003-6)
- Wullenkord, R., & Eyssele, F. (2020). Societal and ethical issues in HRI. *Current Robotics Reports*, 1(3), 85–96. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43154-020-00010-9>
- Wurhofer, D., Meneweger, T., Fuchsberger, V., & Tscheligi, M. (2015). *Deploying robots in a production environment: A study on temporal transitions of workers' experiences*.
- Yam, K. C., Tang, P. M., Jackson, J. C., Su, R., & Gray, K. (2022). The rise of robots increases job insecurity and maladaptive workplace behaviors: Multimethod evidence [Article] *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 108(5), 850–870. <https://doi.org/10.1037/apl0001045>.
- Yuan, S., Coghlan, S., Lederman, R., & Waycott, J. (2022). Social robots in aged care: Care staff experiences and perspectives on robot benefits and challenges [Article] *Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction*, 6(CSCW2), Article 329. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3555220>.